

This is the Submitted Version of the article whose final and definitive form, the Published Version, has been published in *Environmental Science & Policy* [04/08/2021] [copyright Elsevier], available online at:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1462901121002094?dgcid=author>

Reference:

Blázquez, L., García, J. A., & Bodoque, J. M. (2021). Stakeholder analysis: Mapping the river networks for integrated flood risk management. *Environmental Science & Policy*, Vol. 124, 506-516.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.07.024>

Stakeholder Analysis: Mapping the River Networks for Integrated Flood Risk Management

Leticia Blázquez¹, Juan A. García^{2*} & José M. Bodoque³

¹Leticia Blázquez. University of Castilla-La Mancha. Department of Spanish and International Economics, Econometrics and Economic History and Institutions. Faculty of Social Sciences. Avenida de la Real Fábrica de Sedas, s/n. 45600 Talavera de la Reina (Spain). E-mail: Leticia.Blazquez@uclm.es

²Juan A. García. University of Castilla-La Mancha. Department of Business Administration. Faculty of Social Sciences. Avenida de la Real Fábrica de Sedas, s/n. 45600 Talavera de la Reina (Spain). E-mail: Juan.Garcia@uclm.es *Corresponding author.

³José M. Bodoque. University of Castilla-La Mancha. Department of Mining and Geological Engineering. Faculty of Environmental Sciences and Biochemistry. Avenida Carlos III, 45071 Toledo (Spain). E-mail: JoseMaria.Bodoque@uclm.es

Abstract

In recent decades, a change of paradigm in flood risk management (FRM) has been taking place worldwide. The most current legislation and policies reflect this. This change of paradigm implies a gradual transition towards the adoption of more proactive, integrating strategies which require investment in nature-based solutions (NbS) to mitigate flood risk while ensuring the good status of water bodies and restoring river-floodplain systems. To be effective, this transition should be accompanied by an evolution in governance: from top-down approaches to bottom-up schemes in which empowered and well-endowed stakeholder engagement becomes essential. However, the still limited experiences in implementing this combination present numerous potential difficulties and barriers. We use empirical techniques of social network analysis in combination with latent class cluster analysis to diagnose ex-ante these potential challenges to guide policy makers in designing suitable strategies of communication and involvement of stakeholders in the decision-making process. The analysis is carried out in two stages: (i) identifying and examining the relationships of key stakeholders involved in the management, conservation and exploitation of fluvial systems; and (ii) categorising stakeholders according to their perception of the effectiveness of NbS. Only by creating a cohesive and power-balanced river network is it possible to implement just and legitimate FRM strategy.

Keywords

River basin management; bottom-up strategy; stakeholder engagement; nature-based solutions; social network analysis; latent class cluster analysis.

1. Introduction

Traditionally, flood risk management (FRM) has followed a resistance strategy (RS) worldwide, aimed at achieving residual flood risk (Vis et al., 2003). This RS has been primarily based on the implementation of grey infrastructures, which have been complemented by non-structural measures such as land use planning or early warning systems. However, it is becoming increasingly clear that RS proves to be inefficient for several reasons. Firstly, RS has led to the alteration of the hydrological regime of rivers and a subsequent impact on freshwater ecosystems, due mainly to reservoir construction (McCartney, 2009). Secondly, many rivers

globally have been isolated from their floodplains by the presence of levees on the riverbanks (Thoms, 2003). This isolation has entailed a significant increase in the return period of flood pulses (Junk et al., 1989), which is leading to a strong tendency towards terrestrialisation (Amoros and Roux, 1988), which is the main driver of ecosystem services degradation linked to floodplains (Bodoque et al., 2017). Thirdly, this RS creates a false sense of security, i.e., a safe development paradox (Tobin, 1995), which induces owners to invest more in their properties, thereby increasing potential damage in the event of a levee breach.

In response to the abovementioned disadvantages of RS, since the end of the previous century, several milestones have driven a paradigm shift in FRM. This paradigm shift implies that now legislation and policies demand flood risk mitigation to be compatible with the preservation of the good status of water bodies. At the European level, two examples of this new perspective are the Water Framework and the Floods Directives (Quevauviller, 2014). More recently, on December 11th, 2019, the European Green Deal was presented, and one of the actions to be pursued in the framework of the Deal is to restore the natural functions of ground and water surfaces, aiming to prevent and recover biodiversity in aquatic ecosystems, and to prevent and limit flood damage. On a global scale, the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), in particular SDG6 (target 6.6), aim to conserve and restore water-related ecosystems (UN, 2015).

Therefore, FRM is shifting away from the principle of absolute protection to more proactive strategies based on integrated FRM (Hall et al., 2003). Thus, the new policies encourage investment in nature-based solutions, NbS (Nesshöver et al., 2017). They are solutions often more sustainable than traditional grey engineering (Van Wesenbeeck et al., 2014), as NbS provide more multi-functional and flexible solutions, thereby promoting integrated FRM (Vörösmarty et al., 2018). Accordingly, NbS support policies to harmonise objectives that concern flood control and conservation and restoration of freshwater ecosystems (Wharton and Gilvear, 2007). This harmonisation is still a challenge, as current efforts to reverse declines and restore the ecological health of freshwater ecosystems are not achieving the desired outcomes. For example, more than 50% of freshwater bodies in most EU countries are failing to achieve the 'good ecological status' goal set in the Water Framework Directive (Kristensen et al., 2018).

The implementation of these new policies should go hand in hand with a change in the governance of FRM, which is underpinned by better coordination of stakeholder interests with the planning options to be pursued in floodplains (Thaler et al., 2020). To this end, the governance of FRM should evolve from the well-established top-down governance approaches

(Serra-Llobet et al., 2016), to bottom-up initiatives (BUIs), or more inclusive and participatory strategies in which stakeholder engagement becomes essential (Knighton et al., 2018).

In integrated FRM, BUIs can bridge the gap between stakeholders and decision and policy makers, allowing them to raise their interests and concerns through participatory decision-making processes (Thaler and Seebauer, 2019). To facilitate the genesis and operationalisation of BUIs, a certain amount of social capital (Adger, 2003), such as knowledge, motivation/self-interest, networks, organisation and procedural capacity (Kuhlicke et al., 2011), is required. Social capital plays a pivotal role, as it determines to what extent collective action through stakeholder engagement is meaningful. This collective action (Ostrom, 1998) depends primarily on the existence of networks and information flows between stakeholders and policy and decision-makers, determining whether the decision-making architecture under BUIs can be deployed.

A complex socio-environmental issue such as integrated FRM requires systemic, multifaceted interactions between different actors for the successful involvement of stakeholders. (Fliervoet et al., 2013). Each stakeholder has different forms of knowledge (e.g., practical, scientific, management-based, etc.). Consequently, there is a need to foster the conditions for effective cooperation between stakeholders, so that their knowledge, innovations, perspectives, resources and experiences can be harnessed to identify and discuss solutions and new ideas (Benson et al., 2016).

The effectiveness of stakeholder engagement and their positive outcomes can, however, be threatened under certain circumstances. Some scholars mention lack of institutional support and inflexibility, accountability problems, closed culture, timing issues, power inequalities, stakeholders' characteristics (Tseng and Penning-Rowsell, 2012), lack of communication, information sharing, lack of resources in large participation processes (Thaler et al., 2016), frustration (Monnikhof and Edelenbos, 2001), resistance when initiative emerges from governmental agencies (Edelenbos et al., 2017), and different interests and diverging views of each stakeholder group (Lorenzoni and Pidgeon, 2006), even among experts (Knighton et al., 2018). There can also be overrepresentation of specific stakeholder categories in the decision-making process, while others are missing (Reed et al., 2009). The existence of influential lobbies within the social network can lead to the negation of some stakeholders' agendas in favour of others, i.e., lack of procedural justice (Thaler and Levin-Keitel, 2015; Begg, 2018), which potentially leads to or exacerbates conflict (De Vente et al., 2016). Stakeholders sometimes have unrealistically high expectations that have little to do with the objectives of management plans to be developed (Reed, 2008). Another constraint to consider is whether

stakeholder engagement is short-term, which hampers generation of benefits delivered from engagement (Durham et al., 2014). Conversely, stakeholder fatigue and disappointment can occur when engagement is long-term and fails to generate tangible outcomes (Wondolleck and Yaffee, 2000).

Despite their relevance for implementing the policies and strategies described above, there are very few studies that deal with the suitability of BUIs for implementing integrated FRM through NbS (understood here as the restoration of river-floodplain lateral connectivity). To cite some examples, this approach has been adopted as a complementary instrument for dealing with climate change adaptation (Tompkins et al., 2008), in specific frameworks on flood risk decision analysis (Edelenbos et al., 2017; Knighton et al., 2018), or in integrated FRM (Thaler and Levin-Keitel, 2015). However, to the best of our knowledge, there are no published papers that jointly portray stakeholders' perceptions about the meaningfulness of NbS in integrated FRM and the level of interrelationship among stakeholders to achieve the collective asset of mitigating flood risk while ensuring the good status of water bodies and restoring river-floodplain systems. Additionally, the aforementioned papers propose an ex-post evaluation of the case studies they examine, analysing the difficulties found in the implementation of FRM, but none of them offers an empirical framework to detect in advance the characteristics of the stakeholder network.

Aiming to fill this knowledge gap, this study proposes a two-step methodology to make a rigorous diagnosis of the state of the social river network, detecting potential sources of conflicts, divergences or challenges emerging in integrated FRM. Firstly, we study the stakeholders engaged in the management, conservation and exploitation of fluvial systems and the relationships among them. We address this objective in two phases: (i) identification of key stakeholders and (ii) mapping the relationships among them concerning three specific subjects: the river, in general terms; the good (or bad) status of water bodies; and stakeholder perception of flood risk. To address this second phase, we use empirical techniques of social network analysis (SNA) and graph theory, in line with Reed et al. (2009). The second objective is to differentiate and categorise stakeholders into different clusters according to their perception of the effectiveness of NbS and grey infrastructures as management strategies. To do this, we apply latent class cluster analysis (LCCA).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Characteristics of the area of study

The socio-ecological system analysed here is in the reach of the Douro River between Toro and Zamora (Figure 1), to the west of the largest region of Spain (Castilla y León). The Douro is one of the longest Iberian rivers (~927 km), with its source at 1,700 m a.s.l. in the Sierra de Urbión (Iberian Range, Spain) and its mouth at Porto, on the Atlantic coast of Portugal. The drainage basin covers approximately 97,290 km², with 80% in Spain and the remaining 20% in Portugal. The reach studied exhibits a meandering path, which gives its floodplain a high capacity to control floods. Likewise, it is long enough (46.78 km) to test whether the river-floodplain system is as effective as NbS for mitigating floods, ensuring the good status of water bodies and enhancing/recovering ecosystem services.

Six municipalities are included in the area of study. The most important in terms of population are Zamora (61,406 inhabitants) and Toro (8,713 inhabitants). The other four are smaller villages: Villalarbo has 1,821 inhabitants, and the other three (Fresno de la Ribera, Peleagonzalo, and Villalazán) are very tiny villages with fewer than 400 inhabitants. In all of them, a sizable proportion of the population is elderly.

The main economic sector in Zamora is the service sector, which represents around 85% of the employment, while the manufacturing sector employs only 5% of workers. In Toro, the activity which employs the highest number of workers (23%) is the “manufacture of food products, beverages and tobacco products”, followed by “retail trade” (13%) and “agriculture, forestry and fishing” (7.7%). The average annual income both per household and per capita in the five municipalities is lower than the average in Spain, except in Zamora.

Figure 1. Location of the area of study (reach of the Douro River between Toro and Zamora)

2.2. Stakeholder analysis

The conception of stakeholder analysis was guided by the framework proposed by Gilmour and Beilin (2007). It comprises the three actions envisaged by Reed et al. (2009): (1) stakeholder identification; (2) stakeholder relationship analysis; and (3) stakeholder categorisation/differentiation.

2.2.1. Stakeholder identification: participants and instruments

The first stage intended to identify the most prominent stakeholders located in the area of study and engaged in the management, conservation and exploitation of fluvial systems. To do this, ex-ante and ad-hoc approaches (Durham et al., 2014) were used in a complementary manner. Following the ex-ante strategy, stakeholders were identified and categorised (i.e., considering sectors, or groups of relevance) in advance, through a comprehensive literature review complemented by expert knowledge about the area of study. An initial set of stakeholders was then proposed. Alternatively, the identification of stakeholders through the ad-hoc approach was supported by an iterative process, which led to the addition of new

categories of key stakeholders and contacts. A snowball sampling procedure (Gilmour et al., 2011) was applied for this purpose until no new stakeholders were identified.

The database was composed of 63 stakeholders that pertain to four categories: i) national intervention, i.e., military forces organised on a permanent basis for the protection of the environment and to contribute to the security and well-being of citizens; ii) decision makers, i.e., persons who decide things at a high level in local, regional and national administration; iii) civil society, i.e., the space for collective action around shared interests, purposes and values, generally distinct from government and commercial for-profit actors; and iv) economic sectors.

To report the data about each stakeholder, the figure of the key informant was used as a proxy for their organisation, institution or company. A trained interviewer contacted each key informant by telephone or email and invited them to answer an online questionnaire. The fieldwork was carried out during the months of October and November 2019. Figure 2 shows a map of the 47 stakeholders finally surveyed. This number represents a response rate of 74.6%: two national intervenors, 11 decision makers, 18 members of civil society, and 16 economic agents.

Figure 2. Stakeholder map: Actors at national, regional, provincial and local level

The questionnaire consisted of three sections. Following Lara et al. (2010), the first section included nine items regarding the effectiveness of different measures and strategies for mitigating flood risk. These items were rated on a five-point Likert-type scale, ranging from not effective (1) to very effective (5). This section also included a yes/no question regarding the type of interest that each organisation had in the river.

In the second section, three questions were included, asking, respectively, how often each stakeholder: (1) talked to the others about the river overall; (2) talked specifically about the ecological status of the river; and (3) talked specifically about flood risk. The response options ranged from never (0) to many times (4). These answers allowed the construction of three 47 x 47 matrices used as the base input for the SNA.

As a previous step to the SNA, the consistencies/inconsistencies in the frequency of communication reported by each pair of stakeholders were evaluated. Thus, for each stakeholder, it was assessed whether there was agreement or disagreement between their responses to the three questions related to the frequency of communication and those reported by the other 46 counterparts. In cases in which there were discrepancies in the frequency of communication, the values were replaced by the minimum value reported by the two counterparts involved. In this way, three symmetric matrices were constructed.

Finally, the third section gathered socio-demographic information about the key informant (i.e., age, gender, education level, organisation, institution, or company s/he represents, and position).

2.2.2. Stakeholder relationship analysis: social network analysis (SNA)

SNA is based on mathematical graph theory (Wasserman and Faust, 1995). In the graph that represents the river's networks, the vertices of the network correspond to the stakeholders. The lines represent the relationships established between any two stakeholders, considering the adjustments explained in the previous section. Initially, we considered the three river networks (named "talk network", "ecological status network" and "flood risk network") from two complementary standpoints. First, we built a weighted network where each link represented the intensity of relationships reported by each pair of partners. Additionally, we explored the properties of the binary projection of the weighted generic matrix by analysing the mere

presence or absence of a relationship between two stakeholders. The sequence of binary and weighted matrices fully describes the within-sample dynamics of the network, and topological measures and paths can summarise its main characteristics. The corresponding analytical description of this section is presented in Table S1 in the supplementary material. We calculated both aggregate and node-specific network statistics. The aggregate topological measures provide evidence for the structural properties of the whole network. In this vein, the number of partners and the interaction intensity of stakeholders gave a clear idea about the connectivity and integration of participants in the network. Additionally, node-specific network statistics consider individual stakeholders' positions and roles within the network.

2.2.3. Stakeholder categorisation: latent class cluster analysis (LCCA)

To categorise the stakeholders into specific clusters according to their perception of different measures to mitigate flood risk, we performed an LCCA, which is a model-based approach that can be used to identify groups of entities underlying a multivariate data set (Wedel and Kamakura, 2000). Two types of fit indices were used for the selection of the best number of clusters: (1) the Bayesian information criterion (BIC, Schwarz, 1978); and (2) the integrated classification likelihood criterion, estimated using a BIC-type approximation (ICL-BIC, Biernacki et al., 1998). The model proposed included a series of indicators (the nine items related to different measures for mitigating flood risk) and incorporated the stakeholders' sector (nominal variable with six categories: national intervention, decision makers, civil society, agricultural sector, manufacturing sector and service sector) and level (local, provincial, regional and national) as relevant covariates with which to predict cluster membership.

3. Results

3.1. Mapping out the river's stakeholders network

3.1.1. Level of consistency in the frequency of communication reported by stakeholders

The responses obtained with regard to the level of consistency of communication reported by each pair of stakeholders were generally highly consistent: 62% of agreement in the matrix related to talk overall between the values above and below the diagonal, 78% for the matrix

related to ecological status of the river, and 82.1% for the matrix pertaining to flood risk (see Table S2 for complete results for the 47 stakeholders). As shown in Table S2, nine out of 16 stakeholders with disagreements greater than 50% for the talk matrix belonged to the national intervention sector or were decision makers. Five of the latter tended to overestimate the frequency of communication (stakeholders 8, 3, 2, 9 and 5), three were more likely to underestimate it (stakeholders 10, 13 and 12) and one overestimated and underestimated their relationships with the rest of their counterparts in the same proportion (stakeholder 4). In the case of the question about ecological status of the river, two out of three stakeholders with the highest disagreement were decision makers (stakeholders 10 and 8). Finally, in the case of flood risk, the only stakeholder with discrepancies greater than 50% was also a decision maker (stakeholder 10).

3.1.2. Network structure

We started the analysis by studying the aggregate statistics of the three binary networks (see Table S1 for definitions). Table 1 and Figure 3 reveal that the three networks are quite loose, although the talk network is denser than the other two, with the flood risk network the least dense: in this last network, out of the possible links between stakeholders, only 1.9% take place (2.1% in the ecological status and 7.3% in the talk network).

Table 1. Topological measures of the river network

Indicator	Talk	Ecological status	Flood risk
Lines	158	45	41
Density	0.073	0.021	0.019
Average degree	6.72	1.91	1.74
All Degree centralisation	0.39	0.23	0.19
Closeness centrality (Average)	0.4077	0.1232	0.1005
Betweenness centrality (Average)	0.0043	0.0011	0.0005
Betweenness centralisation	0.030	0.0214	0.0081
CLC1 (CLC2) (Average)	0.23 (0.19)	0.25 (0.14)	0.17 (0.13)
K-core	(k=7) 20	(k=3) 11	(k=3)11

We also observe that the talk network, although not very extensive, is much more extensive than the other two networks. On average, its stakeholders have contact with 6.72 other stakeholders, in contrast to the 1.91 and 1.74 of the ecological status and flood risk networks, respectively.

Furthermore, according to the results for aggregate centrality measures (Table 1), the three networks respond to a traditional centre-periphery structure in terms of connectivity and intensity. This indicates that there are small groups of more connected stakeholders in the centre with relationships with a higher number of other actors, and with most of the stakeholders on the periphery, either having a very small number of partners —most of them the central stakeholders— or completely disconnected.

Figure 3. River Networks. The size of the nodes (stakeholders) is related to their total number of links (*all node degrees*)

Additionally, we observe that only a few stakeholders play the important role of intermediary (Newman, 2005; Fisher and Vega-Redondo, 2006) within the networks and, hence, become crucial for the integration of the network. Besides, we detect that distances between stakeholders seem to be much shorter in the talk network than in the other two, insofar as more direct relationships are observed within that general network. Particularly far from each other are the stakeholders in the flood risk network.

Concerning the extent to which stakeholders are clustered, we observe that within the talk and ecological status networks, there are around 25% of all possible triangular relationships, while this portion is lower for the flood risk network (17%). We also appreciate that the most connected actors' partners are not necessarily connected themselves.

We also identified relatively dense subnetworks and thus cohesive subgroups within the networks (see Figure S1). Within the talk network, we detect a wide subnetwork that contains 20 stakeholders strongly connected with each other. Indeed, those are the crucial actors within the network: one of the two national intervenors, many decision makers, some civil society members, and only one productive sector stakeholder, which happens to be a state service company. The scenario is quite different for the other two networks: in both, the densest subnetworks are smaller, (11 stakeholders, almost the same ones in both) with a weaker connection between them. The almost null participation of the economic sector in the three networks is quite remarkable.

3.1.3. Who is who in the river social networks?

We now focus on the individual characteristics of the stakeholders within the network. Table S3 shows the main indicators for the 47 actors. First considering the more general talk network, we observe that there are 12 stakeholders which have between 10 and 24 contacts, another 12 between 5 and 10, and the other 23 with fewer than 5 contacts, with two actors completely disconnected. In the group of the most connected stakeholders, we have one of the national intervenors, the one most closely related to the environmental areas, and six decision makers, most of them public institutions directly related to river technical management or environment, tourism, or agricultural and fishing areas. Finally, within this more connected group, we also find some members of civil society like unions or the provincial Chamber of Commerce. We also

have mainly productive companies, some of which belong to the sector of environmental and tourism services, and one consumer association.

As for the ecological status network, only two stakeholders have more than 10 contacts, another three have five or more, and 21 (out of 47) do not have any contact at all with the rest of the network. The two most connected stakeholders are two decision makers, both public institutions directly involved in the administration of the river, one at the provincial level and the other at the regional level, with those stakeholders also very connected in the talk network. Similarly, another three with more than three contacts are institutional decision makers also very connected in the talk network. Concerning the stakeholders that are completely disconnected, there are mostly productive companies, but also some members of civil society, like consumer associations, regional universities or parish churches. Moreover, there are decision makers, such as civil protection or the supra-local administration.

Finally, within the flood risk network, only one stakeholder has 10 contacts: one state technical manager of the river. We have five more actors with five or more contacts, four of which are national decision makers directly involved in river management. There are 23 disconnected nodes; again, most of them are members of productive sectors (13) and a few are civil society actors (9). Once again, the supra-local administration reports no contacts.

When we correlated some of their indicators (see Figures S2, S3 and S4), we observed that while for the talk network the most connected stakeholders are the ones most closely connected, this positive relation is much weaker for the flood risk network and is almost insignificant for the ecological status network. In the three networks, it is observed that not only are there few stakeholders with a high number of links, but there are even fewer that are closely connected. Additionally, the most connected nodes are those that are more easily reachable, although, again, the relation is positive but not highly significant. This direct correlation is stronger in the case of the ecological status. Finally, we have detected that, for all three networks, the stakeholders that have a higher number of connections and are more integrated are, in general, also the ones who play a more prominent role as intermediaries within the networks. The relation is positive in all three cases, although weakly significant. Again, the strongest relation is observed for the ecological status.

3.2. Grouping the stakeholders according to the perceived effectiveness of flood risk mitigation measures

As mentioned, an LCCA was used to group the stakeholders according to the perceived effectiveness of nine flood risk mitigation measures. The first step in the LCCA is the choice of the best model. Five models were considered, each of which featured between one (sample homogeneity) and five clusters. The results showed in Table 2 indicate that there are three clusters of stakeholders according to the BIC and ICL-BIC. Following the procedure suggested by García (2017), we estimated each model 10 times with different random start values, and the superiority of the model with three clusters was found to be the most consistent.

Table 2. Fit indices for the latent class cluster models tested: relative fit index and classification-based information criterion

Model	Log-likelihood (LL)	BIC(LL)	ICL-BIC	Number of Parameters	Classification Errors
1 cluster	-663.780	1396.862	1396.862	18	0.000
2 clusters	-610.276	1393.808	1396.404	45	0.007
3 clusters*	-556.986	1391.182	1393.193	72	0.007
4 clusters	-526.954	1435.072	1436.695	99	0.005
5 clusters	-489.726	1464.571	1466.253	126	0.004

Notes: BIC: Bayesian information criterion, ICL-BIC: integrated classification likelihood criterion estimated using a BIC-type approximation, *Best model according to BIC and ICL-BIC.

The second step is the assessment of the significance of the indicators and the covariates (see Table S4). The *p-value* associated with the robust Wald statistic was less than 0.05 for eight out of nine indicators proposed, indicating that the perceived effectiveness of these flood risk mitigation measures varied between the three clusters. Concerning the covariates, significant effects were observed based on the stakeholders' sector and level ($p < 0.05$). Table 3 presents the profiles of the three clusters of stakeholders, while Table S5 in the supplementary material includes an extensive list of the stakeholders included in each cluster. A summary of the features of these three clusters is presented below:

Cluster 1. Sceptics. This first cluster is the most numerous, representing 46.8% of the sample (a total of 22 stakeholders; see Table S5). Stakeholders in this group tend to assess the perceived effectiveness of different mitigation measures below the total sample mean, with the only exceptions being measures related to dredging the river and building new levees (in both cases with scores close to the sample mean). Approximately 45% of Cluster 1 are members of

civil society. This cluster has the highest proportion of stakeholders engaged in the manufacturing and service sectors (40.9%). In addition, local stakeholders predominate in Cluster 1 (54.5%). Along with Cluster 2, Cluster 1 has the highest proportion of national stakeholders (22.7%).

Cluster 2. *Enthusiasts of NbS and stakeholder engagement.* This group, which represents 27.7% of the sample (13 stakeholders), perceives high effectiveness of mitigation measures related to making room for the river, forbidding urban development in flood-prone areas and encouraging community participation in FRM, but very low effectiveness of other structural measures related to dredging the river and building new levees and reservoirs. More than nine out of 10 stakeholders in this group are part of civil society (mainly environmental NGOs, consumer associations and universities) or decision makers. Regional stakeholders (46.2%) are the majority with respect to those at other levels.

Cluster 3. *Defenders of holistic approaches.* This last group represents 25.5% of the sample (12 stakeholders) and its main distinguishing feature is the perceived high effectiveness of almost all mitigation measures. The two national intervenors surveyed are in this cluster and, within the productive sectors, agricultural and service companies represent a higher percentage than in the other clusters. Half of these are local stakeholders, although the importance of provincial stakeholders is significantly higher than in the other two clusters. The only two national stakeholders in this group are the state intervenors.

Table 3. Profiles for the three clusters of stakeholders

Variable	Cluster 1. Sceptics (46.8%)	Cluster 2. Enthusiasts of NbS and stakeholder engagement (27.7%)	Cluster 3. Defenders of holistic approaches (25.5%)	Total
Indicators (M)				
Dredging the river	2.6	1.2	4.1	2.6
Building new levees	2.7	1.4	3.5	2.5
Building reservoirs	2.7	2.1	4.0	2.9
Dam removal	2.2	2.9	3.2	2.7
Riparian restoration	3.6	4.1	4.2	3.9
Making room for the river	2.6	4.8	4.2	3.7
Forbidding urban development in flood-prone areas	3.6	4.7	4.5	4.1
Flood emergency response plan	3.9	4.3	4.9	4.3
Community participation in flood risk management	3.5	4.5	4.8	4.1
Covariates (%)				
<i>Sector</i>				
National intervenors	0.0%	0.0%	16.7%	4.3%
Decision makers	13.6%	46.2%	16.7%	23.4%
Civil society	45.5%	46.2%	16.7%	38.3%
Primary sector	0.0%	7.7%	8.3%	4.3%
Secondary sector	13.6%	0.0%	8.3%	8.5%
Tertiary sector	27.3%	0.0%	33.3%	21.3%
<i>Level</i>				
Local	54.5%	23.1%	50.0%	44.7%
Provincial	9.1%	7.7%	25.0%	12.8%
Regional	13.6%	46.2%	8.3%	21.3%
National	22.7%	23.1%	16.7%	21.3%

Note: For the indicators, the values marked with different colours indicate statistically significant differences in the means among the clusters based on paired comparison analyses. For the covariates, the highest percentages per row are shown in boldface.

Once we know what the perception of the stakeholders is concerning the effectiveness of the different flood risk mitigation measures, it is interesting to study whether their perceptions are related to their main interests in the issues concerning the river. In the questionnaire, we included this question, with four possible options. The results are shown in Table 4. We observed that association between the cluster and the interest exists in only two cases: FRM and environmental and biological diversity conservation. In the case of FRM, around half of the stakeholders that belong to the cluster of enthusiasts of NbS and stakeholder engagement are interested in FRM, while among the sceptical stakeholders and the defenders of holistic

approaches only between 9-16% are interested in this issue. In the case of interest in environmental and biological diversity conservation, 77% of the stakeholders that belong to cluster 2 (enthusiasts) are interested in this subject, while in cluster 3 (defenders of holistic approaches), half of the stakeholders showed interest in it, and a third in the case of the sceptical stakeholders.

Table 4. Differences in cluster interest

Interest (% Yes)	Cluster 1. Sceptics	Cluster 2. Enthusiasts of NbS and stakeholder engagement	Cluster 3. Defenders of holistic approaches	Fisher's Exact Test (p)
Water resource management	22.7%	53.8%	16.7%	4.645 (0.090)
Flood risk management	9.1%	46.2%	16.7%	6.183 (0.043)
Environmental and biological diversity conservation	31.8%	76.9%	50.0%	6.567 (0.042)
Water availability, supply, and consumption	54.5%	61.5%	75.0%	1.306 (0.286)

Finally, we studied whether statistically significant differences exist among stakeholders' SNA topological scores depending on their interests (Table 5). We found that stakeholders interested in water resource management are the most clustered in the talk and ecological status networks. We also detected that stakeholders interested in FRM are the most strongly connected stakeholders in the talk and risk flood networks and the ones who are closer to each other and more clustered within the ecological status and risk flood networks. Lastly, stakeholders interested in environmental and biological diversity conservation are the most strongly connected in the ecological network. Therefore, we can affirm that stakeholders' interests will influence the manner and the extent to which they become involved in the river networks.

Table 5. Significant differences in the topological indicators for each interest

Interest	T-test for independent samples (M, t, p)
Water resource management	<p>Clustering coefficient:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talk ($M_{NO} = 0.1671$; $M_{YES} = 0.2797$, $t = -2.442$, $p = 0.019$) • Ecological ($M_{NO} = 0.0539$, $M_{YES} = 0.2335$, $t = -3.130$, $p = 0.006$)
Flood risk management	<p>All Degree:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talk ($M_{NO} = 5.7297$, $M_{YES} = 10.4000$, $t = -2.469$, $p = 0.017$) • Risk ($M_{NO} = 1.000$, $M_{YES} = 4.5000$, $t = -4.824$, $p = 0.000$) <p>Closeness Centrality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological ($M_{NO} = 0.0999$, $M_{YES} = 0.2094$, $t = -3.417$, $p = 0.003$) • Risk ($M_{NO} = 0.072$, $M_{YES} = 0.2057$, $t = -4.542$, $p = 0.000$) <p>Clustering coefficient:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological ($M_{NO} = 0.0999$, $M_{YES} = 0.2094$, $t = -3.259$, $p = 0.002$) • Risk ($M_{NO} = 0.0352$, $M_{YES} = 0.1578$, $t = -2.928$, $p = 0.005$)
Environmental and biological diversity conservation	<p>All Degree:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological ($M_{NO} = 1.042$, $M_{YES} = 2.8261$, $t = -2,283$, $p = 0.030$)

4. Discussion

Environmental applications of SNA are just beginning to emerge. Only a few works have evaluated ex post the role of all engaged stakeholders within the network and how their positions can help to better design policies and strategies for environmental management with special relevance for complex, long-term tasks like FRM (e.g., Prell et al., 2009; Thaler and Levin-Keitel, 2015; Edelenbos et al., 2017; Knighton et al., 2018). In this regard, to the best of our knowledge, the research undertaken here represents the first attempt to apply a methodological framework which allows us to make an ex-ante diagnosis of the state of the social river network. By identifying the obstacles and barriers, but also the strengths, that can arise in the implementation of FRM based on NbS through the adoption of a suitable bottom-up strategy, decision makers can design a procedure tailored to the needs of the network analysed. In this regard, the results presented in Section 3 raise some interesting and worrying issues.

From the SNA, we detected, in general, very scarce and non-intense relationships among stakeholders within the river networks. In this context, it is reasonable to assume that the potential for developing co-production decision-making processes, collaborative actions or resolutions of conflicts, contained in BUI strategy, will be low. If only a few stakeholders are connected and not even very intensely with the others, and, as we saw, their partners are not

necessarily connected themselves, and if more than half of the relevant actors are completely out, then it is very unlikely that the strategies or actions coming from any direction will spread out across the networks.

Among the main requisites for local stakeholders to become involved in the discussion and decision-making process are possession of a certain capacity and resources to act, and also interest and social and cultural capital (Kuhlicke et al., 2011). However, what our analysis showed was that most of the local and supra-local stakeholders are not connected at all within the network. Therefore, the first action to take is to raise local-disconnected stakeholders' awareness that they are active stakeholders of the river network, insofar as they may be affected by or may have interests in the issues related to the river, and because they can be involved in the decision-making process. This awareness will empower them and provide them with the ability to ensure their interests (Kruse and Seidl, 2013; Thaler and Levin-Keitel, 2015). In this first stage, national and regional authorities will be the leaders of the decision-making process. They will define its conditions and objectives, and they will be responsible for integrating the rest of the stakeholders into the BUI approach and encouraging them to contribute and participate. Thus, the success of this partnership strategy will depend greatly on their political willingness and flexibility. Building trust is their main objective, especially between stakeholders who have never collaborated in the past (Thaler and Levin-Keitel, 2015).

From a practical point of view, these national and regional authorities must focus on the design and implementation of communication strategies targeted at stakeholders. First, the group called sceptics (Cluster 1) should be the main target audience because of its large size (approximately half the sample) and its profile in relation to the perceived low effectiveness of different flood risk mitigation measures. As we saw, most of these stakeholders are not involved at all in the problems of the river and are not even aware of how they can be affected by issues related to it, such as FRM. Therefore, design awareness actions aimed at civil society (linked mainly to trade unions, agricultural associations, architects' associations or religious institutions, as shown in Table S5) and the secondary and tertiary sectors seem to have great potential to increase the effectiveness of measures related to NbS. The main objective is to make them understand that they have strong interdependent interest with the rest of the stakeholders, related, for example, to land use management and the NBSs, which can cause conflict between

them (Knighton et al, 2018), and to transmit to them clearly how they can participate in the co-production decision-making process.

In the design of the communication strategy, it is important that technical and political authorities reach a certain consensus about key issues like what socioeconomic losses a flood entails, anticipated community needs, community perception of risk, impacts of the different NbS, etc. It is necessary to adequately communicate these risks and impacts to the rest of the stakeholders and to facilitate decisions by policy makers. Some studies have shown that there are substantial disconnections between public perceptions and expert opinions, but, also, between experts themselves (Knighton et al., 2018). In our analysis of the river networks, these more technical stakeholders are closely connected, so it is expected that those links will be useful for establishing common understanding of community vulnerabilities and impacts of the NbS.

The cluster called enthusiasts of NbS and stakeholder engagement (Cluster 2) includes the national and regional authorities who will lead the process, but also other stakeholders that, rather than being a target audience, should take an active role as key partners. There are two reasons for this: (1) they have internalised the FRM approaches that are close to those that should be promoted; and (2) they are reasonably well-connected with the other stakeholders, and, more importantly, they are the gatekeepers within the networks and part of a cohesive subgroup. In this sense, ensuring that local and provincial decision makers, foundations linked to water management, environmental associations, consumer associations and universities feel involved in the communication strategy designed will encourage them to act as evangelisers or collaborators of the same. This more cohesive network could be used as leverage for introducing the BUI strategy within the network. Because of their condition, together with national and national governmental stakeholders, they are the only ones with the necessary social and cultural capital to lead and develop the co-production decision-making.

Finally, the defenders of holistic approaches (Cluster 3) should also be considered in the design and implementation of the communication strategy for both their profile and their high interrelation with other actors (especially in the case of national intervenors and the Zamora provincial council).

This process of empowerment and engagement of stakeholders should result in the creation of a local storyline, hopefully aligned with the framework of higher-level narrative (Nilson et al., 2017). The second step would then be that, gradually, local/provincial stakeholders, both authorities and non-state, start to cooperate with each other, and national and regional authorities would focus more on project monitoring and controlling (Thaler and Levin-Keitel, 2015). Local and provincial stakeholders became an equal player in the co-production decision-making with national and regional authorities, although, given the governmental structure of water management in Spain, these higher-level authorities will likely keep a major part of the initiative. For this reason, at this stage, the strength of local leadership is very relevant. Especially important are local grassroots organisations as they can modify the behaviour of the national authorities and other local stakeholders (Thaler and Levin-Keitel, 2015). In our river network, the ecologist might play that influential role.

Once all local and provincial stakeholders are involved in the FRM and transmuted into Cluster 2, their role could be much more proactive. As long as they are able to develop sufficient social and cultural capital (knowledge, information, networks, collaboration with experts, media, lobbies, financial support and time) (Kuhlicke et al., 2011), they could develop their own plan and initiatives in a constructive manner. In this scenario, governmental actors are supposed to be more inclined to positively respond to stakeholders' initiatives, which, in turn, will increase the chances that their interest is included and represented in the general FRM strategy (Thaler and Levin-Keitel, 2015; Edelenbos et al., 2017).

In this dynamic procedure, it is expected that stakeholders become more and more involved from the early stages of the co-creation process, when they can have real influence and impact. It is also expected that national and regional policymakers positively receive and integrate the proposal and initiatives of local stakeholders after the co-creation process, and that they perceive that their interests and preferences are de facto included in the measures adopted, plans developed and decisions made by governmental decision-makers (Doorn, 2016; Edelenbos et al., 2017).

As a result of this whole process, the actual core-periphery structure that the river networks describe should be substituted for a regular shape in which all the actors show more balanced numbers and closeness of links. Moreover, the high homophily of central stakeholders that we

observed within the existing networks will be eliminated. The whole network will be enriched with new ideas, resources, and more complete, holistic and useful information. These wider and more diverse relationships will promote trust, reciprocity, collaboration and involvement of different stakeholders in the complex actions needed for FRM and will make the network more resilient and flexible for facing environmental changes (Hahn et al., 2006; Ramirez-Sanchez, 2007; Sandström, 2008; Bodin and Crona, 2009; Prell et al., 2009).

This kind of participatory process in FRM involves the sharing of responsibility between the state across different levels of society and is linked to the concept of procedural justice (Begg, 2018). We can presume that if local stakeholders have actively participated in the decision-making process, they are more likely to accept state interventions, take action to prepare and protect themselves and find resources for FRM (Adger et al., 2016; Begg, 2018). Nevertheless, it seems that participatory strategy does not promote a fair distribution of risk, as the more vulnerable communities are usually disadvantaged by decision-making processes (Begg, 2018). In our river networks, the supra-local and provincial authorities would be responsible for ensuring the participation of these less influential, usually rural, stakeholders in the process on an equal footing and the defense of their interests. Ultimately, this accountability of all stakeholders and balance of power is tied to the concept of legitimacy, which is required to increase the quality of the governance output (Scharpf, 1998; Alexander et al., 2018). It could be a problem if the stakeholders on the periphery feel that they have been marginalised in decision-making areas and that only a set of centrally positioned actors define the agenda on behalf of the majority of network members (Diani, 2003; Ernstson et al., 2008; Bodin and Crona, 2009; Vallet et al., 2020).

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we have proposed a methodological framework based on the combination of social network analysis (SNA) and latent class cluster analysis (LCCA) to diagnose the potential difficulties that can arise in designing an appropriate (and mandatory) bottom-up initiative (BUI) approach of governance for Flood Risk Management (FRM) based on nature-based solutions (NbS). We have also proposed a strategy to deal with the challenges and complexities that we have found in our river network. The problems are basically that existing networks are not very

extensive and are poorly cohesive, with many stakeholders completely disconnected from river issues. Accordingly, we have found a large group of stakeholders who are sceptical about the effectiveness of the NbS. To overcome these difficulties, a gradual and robust strategy of communication and engagement must be led by the central stakeholders of the network, mainly national and regional stakeholders, but also some local/provincial members of civil society who must act as a boundaries stakeholder. They have the necessary social and cultural capital to head the plan and to engage the other actors in the decision process. Only when a cohesive network is created, with most of the local stakeholders engaged and well-represented in the BUI and really convinced of the virtues and qualities of the NbS, can effective FRM be applied. Also, only when all these stronger and more extended links are created will the common understanding, assimilation and acceptance of the necessary policies and actions to take be implemented, as they will be procedurally just and legitimate.

We applied our analysis to the specific case of the Douro River, in Spain, but the scheme can be easily applied to other scenarios insofar as similar stakeholders' structures, state and non-state, conflicting interests and vulnerabilities can be found in most rivers.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Leticia Blázquez: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing - original draft. **Juan A. García:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing - review & editing. **José M. Bodoque:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - review & editing, Visualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

This research has been funded by the projects DRAINAGE (CGL2017- 83546-C3-1-R/MINEICO/AEI/FEDER, UE) of the Spanish National Plan for Scientific and Technical Research and Innovation and ADaPTAR (SBPLY/17/180501/000416/JCCM/FEDER, UE) of the

Regional Government of the Autonomous Region of Castilla-La Mancha. We also thank Estefania Aranda Cordoba for conveying the questionnaires to stakeholders by email and phone.

Supplementary material

Table S1. Statistical definitions for SNA.

Table S2. Level of consistency in the frequency of communication reported by the 47 stakeholders.

Table S3. Description of the individual characteristics of the 47 stakeholders within the networks: node-specific network statistics.

Table S4. Parameters estimated for the three clusters of stakeholders.

Table S5. List of the stakeholders included in each cluster based on the LCCA.

Figure S1. K-cores. The size of the nodes is related to their total number of links. They are the densest subnetwork within each network: the maximum subnetwork in which each node has at least degree k .

Figure S2. Correlation between *Node Degree* and *Node Strength* for the three river networks.

Figure S3. Correlation between *Node Degree* and the *Closeness Centrality Index* for the three river networks.

Figure S4. Correlation between *Node Degree* and *Random Walk Betweenness Centrality* for the three river networks.

References

Adger, W.N., 2003. Social capital, collective action, and adaptation to climate change. *Econ. Geogr.* 79, 387–404.

- Adger, W.N., Quinn, T., Lorenzoni, I., Murphy, C., 2016. Sharing the pain: Perceptions of fairness affect private and public response to hazards. *Ann. Am. Assoc. Geogr.* 106, 1079–1096. doi:10.1080/24694452.2016.1182005
- Alexander, M., Doorn, N., Priest, S., 2018. Bridging the legitimacy gap—translating theory into practical signposts for legitimate flood risk governance. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 18, 397–408. doi:10.1007/s10113-017-1195-4
- Amoros, C., Roux, A., 1988. Interaction between water bodies within the floodplains of large rivers: Function and development of connectivity. *münstersche Geogr. Arb.* 29, 125–130.
- Begg, C., 2018. Power, responsibility and justice: A review of local stakeholder participation in European flood risk management. *Local Environ.* 23, 383–397. doi:10.1080/13549839.2017.1422119
- Benson, D., Lorenzoni, I., Cook, H., 2016. Evaluating social learning in England flood risk management: An “individual-community interaction” perspective. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 55, 326–334. doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2015.05.013
- Biernacki, C., Celeux, G., Govaert, G., 1998. Assessing a mixture model for cluster with the integrated classification likelihood (Tech. Rep. No.3521). Rhône-Alpes, France.
- Bodin, Ö., Crona, B.I., 2009. The role of social networks in natural resource governance: What relational patterns make a difference? *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 19, 366–374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2009.05.002>
- Bodoque, J.M., Ladera, J., Yela, J.L., Alonso-Azcárate, J., Brito, D., Antigüedad, I., Duran, R., Attard, E., Lauga, B., Sánchez-Pérez, J.M., 2017. Recovering hydromorphological functionality to improve natural purification capacity of a highly human-modified wetland. *Ecol. Eng.* 103, 332–343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2016.02.013>
- Devente, J., Reed, M.S., Stringer, L.C., Valente, S., Newig, J., 2016. How does the context and design of participatory decision making processes affect their outcomes? Evidence from sustainable land management in global drylands. *Ecol. Soc.* 21. doi:10.5751/ES-08053-210224
- Diani, M., 2003. Networks and social movements: A research programme, in: Diani, M., McAdam, D. (Eds.), *Social Movements and Networks: Relational Approaches to Collective*

- Action. University Press, Oxford, pp. 299–319.
- Doorn, N., 2016. Governance experiments in water management: From interests to building blocks. *Sci. Eng. Ethics* 22, 755–774. doi:10.1007/s11948-015-9627-3
- Durham, E., Baker, H., Smith, M., Moore, E., Morgan, V., 2014. The BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook, BiodivERsA. ed. BiodivERsA, Paris.
- Edelenbos, J., Van Buuren, A., Roth, D., Winnubst, M., 2017. Stakeholder initiatives in flood risk management: Exploring the role and impact of bottom-up initiatives in three ‘Room for the River’ projects in the Netherlands. *J. Environ. Plan. Manag.* 60, 47–66. doi:10.1080/09640568.2016.1140025
- Ernstson, H., Sörlin, S., Elmqvist, T., 2008. Social movements and ecosystem services - The role of social network structure in protecting and managing urban green areas in Stockholm. *Ecol. Soc.* 13. <https://doi.org/10.5751/es-02589-130239>
- Fisher, E., Vega-Redondo, F., 2006. The Linchpins of a Modern Economy 18.
- Fliervoet, J.M., Van den Born, R.J.G., Smits, A.J.M., Knippenberg, L., 2013. Combining safety and nature: A multi-stakeholder perspective on integrated floodplain management. *J. Environ. Manage.* 128, 1033–1042. doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.06.023
- García, J.A., 2017. Time use patterns of Spanish people at weekends: In search of what, who and when. *Leis. Stud.* 36, 793–810. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/02614367.2016.1252786>
- Gilmour, J., Beilin, R., 2007. Stakeholder mapping for effective risk assessment and communication, Australian Centre of Excellence for Risk Analysis.
- Gilmour, P.W., Dwyer, P.D., Day, R.W., 2011. Beyond individual quotas: The role of trust and cooperation in promoting stewardship of five Australian abalone fisheries. *Mar. Policy* 35, 692–702. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2011.02.010>
- Hahn, T., Olsson, P., Folke, C., Johansson, K., 2006. Trust-building, knowledge generation and organizational innovations: The role of a bridging organization for adaptive comanagement of a wetland landscape around Kristianstad, Sweden. *Hum. Ecol.* 34, 573–592. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-006-9035-z>
- Hall, J.W., Meadowcroft, I.C., Sayers, P.B., Bramley, M.E., 2003. Integrated flood risk

- management in England and Wales. *Nat. Hazards Rev.* 4, 126–135.
[https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1527-6988\(2003\)4:3\(126\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1527-6988(2003)4:3(126))
- Junk, W.J., Bayley, P.B., Sparks, R.E., 1989. The flood pulse concept in river-floodplain systems. *Can. J. Fish. Aquat. Sci.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2012.10.032>
- Knighton, J.O., Tsuda, O., Elliott, R., Todd Walter, M., 2018. Challenges to implementing bottom-up flood risk decision analysis frameworks: How strong are social networks of flooding professionals? *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 22, 5657–5673.
<https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-22-5657-2018>
- Kristensen, P., Whalley, C., Zal, F.N., Christiansen, T., 2018. European waters assessment of status and pressures 2018. *Eur. Environ. Agency.* doi:10.2800/303664
- Kruse, S., Seidl, I., 2013. Social capacities for drought risk management in Switzerland. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 13, 3429–3441. doi:10.5194/nhess-13-3429-2013
- Kuhlicke, C., Steinführer, A., Begg, C., Bianchizza, C., Bründl, M., Buchecker, M., De Marchi, B., Di Masso Tarditti, M., Höppner, C., Komac, B., Lemkow, L., Luther, J., McCarthy, S., Pellizzoni, L., Renn, O., Scolobig, A., Supramaniam, M., Tapsell, S., Wachinger, G., Walker, G., Whittle, R., Zorn, M., Faulkner, H., 2011. Perspectives on social capacity building for natural hazards: Outlining an emerging field of research and practice in Europe. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 14, 804–814. doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2011.05.001
- Lara, A., Saurí, D., Ribas, A., Pavón, D., 2010. Social perceptions of floods and flood management in a Mediterranean area (Costa Brava, Spain). *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 10, 2081–2091. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-10-2081-2010>
- Lorenzoni, I., Pidgeon, N.F., 2006. Public views on climate change: European and USA perspectives. *Clim. Change* 77, 73–95. doi:10.1007/s10584-006-9072-z
- Newman, L., Dale, A., 2005. Network structure, diversity, and proactive resilience building: A response to Tompkins and Adger. *Ecol. Soc.* 10, 0–4. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-01396-1001r02>
- McCartney, M., 2009. Living with dams: Managing the environmental impacts. *Water Policy* 11, 121–139. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wp.2009.108>
- Monnikhof, R.A.H., Edelenbos, J., 2001. Into the fog? Stakeholder input in participatory impact

- assessment. *Impact Assess. Proj. Apprais.* 19, 29–39. doi:10.3152/147154601781767212
- Nesshöver, C., Assmuth, T., Irvine, K.N., Rusch, G.M., Waylen, K.A., Delbaere, B., Haase, D., Jones-Walters, L., Keune, H., Kovacs, E., Krauze, K., Külvik, M., Rey, F., van Dijk, J., Vistad, O.I., Wilkinson, M.E., Wittmer, H., 2017. The science, policy and practice of nature-based solutions: An interdisciplinary perspective. *Sci. Total Environ.* 579, 1215–1227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.11.106>
- Nilsson, A.E., Bay-Larsen, I., Carlsen, H., van Oort, B., Bjørkan, M., Jylhä, K., Klyuchnikova, E., Masloboev, V., van der Watt, L.M., 2017. Towards extended shared socioeconomic pathways: A combined participatory bottom-up and top-down methodology with results from the Barents region. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 45, 124–132. doi:10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.06.001.
- Ostrom, E., 1998. A Behavioral Approach to the Rational Choice Theory of Collective Action: Presidential Address, American Political Science Association, 1997 Author(s): Elinor Ostrom Source: *The American Political Science Review* , Vol . 92 , No . 1 (Mar ., 1998),. *Am. Polit. Sci. Rev.* 92, 1–22.
- Prell, C., Hubacek, K., Reed, M., 2009. Stakeholder analysis and social network analysis in natural resource management. *Soc. Nat. Resour.* 22, 501–518. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920802199202>
- Quevauviller, P., 2014. European water policy and research on water-related topics - An overview. *J. Hydrol.* 518, 180–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2014.02.007>
- Ramirez-Sanchez, S., 2007. A social relational approach to the conservation and management of fisheries: The rural communities of the Loreto Bay National Marine Park, BCS, Mexico. ProQuest Diss. Theses. Simon Fraser University.
- Reed, M.S., 2008. Stakeholder participation for environmental management: A literature review. *Biol. Conserv.* 141, 2417–2431. doi:10.1016/j.biocon.2008.07.014
- Reed, M.S., Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., Prell, C., Quinn, C.H., Stringer, L.C., 2009. Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. *J. Environ. Manage.* 90, 1933–1949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2009.01.001>
- Sandström, A., 2008. Policy networks: The Relation between Structure and Performance. ~~Dr.~~

- PhD Thesis. Luleå University of Technology.
- Scharpf, F.W., 1998. MPIfG Working Paper 98/2, Fritz W. Scharpf: Interdependence and Democratic Legitimation 1–21.
- Schwarz, G., 1978. Estimating the dimension of a model. *Ann. Stat.* 6, 461–464.
- Serra-Llobet, A., Conrad, E., Schaefer, K., 2016. Governing for integrated water and flood risk management: Comparing top-down and bottom-up approaches in Spain and California. *Water (Switzerland)* 8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w8100445>
- Thaler, T., Levin-keitel, M., 2015. ScienceDirect Multi-level stakeholder engagement in flood risk management — A question of roles and power: Lessons from England. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 55, 292–301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.04.007>
- Thaler, T.A., Priest, S.J., Fuchs, S., 2016. Evolving inter-regional co-operation in flood risk management: Distances and types of partnership approaches in Austria. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 16, 841–853. doi:10.1007/s10113-015-0796-z
- Thaler, T., Seebauer, S., 2019. Bottom-up citizen initiatives in natural hazard management: Why they appear and what they can do? *Environ. Sci. Policy* 94, 101–111. doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2018.12.012
- Thaler, T., Nordbeck, R., Löschner, L., Seher, W., 2020. Cooperation in flood risk management: Understanding the role of strategic planning in two Austrian policy instruments. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 114, 170–177. doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2020.08.001
- Thoms, M.C., 2003. Floodplain-river ecosystems: Lateral connections and the implications of human interference. *Geomorphology* 56, 335–349. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-555X\(03\)00160-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-555X(03)00160-0)
- Tobin, G.A., 1995. The levee love affair: A stormy relationship. *JAWRA J. Am. Water Resour. Assoc.* 31, 359–367. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-1688.1995.tb04025.x>
- Tompkins, E.L., Few, R., Brown, K., 2008. Scenario-based stakeholder engagement: Incorporating stakeholders preferences into coastal planning for climate change. *J. Environ. Manage.* 88, 1580–1592. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2007.07.025>
- Tseng, C.P., Penning-Rowsell, E.C., 2012. Micro-political and related barriers to stakeholder engagement in flood risk management. *Geogr. J.* 178, 253–269. doi:10.1111/j.1475-

- UN, 2015. Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Resolution adopted by the General Assembly [WWW Document]. UN (United Nations).
- Vallet, A., Locatelli, B., Barnaud, C., Makowski, D., Quispe Conde, Y., Levrel, H., 2020. Power asymmetries in social networks of ecosystem services governance. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 114, 329–340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.08.020>
- Van Wesenbeeck, B.K., Mulder, J.P.M., Marchand, M., Reed, D.J., De Vries, M.B., De Vriend, H.J., Herman, P.M.J., 2014. Damming deltas: A practice of the past? Towards nature-based flood defenses. *Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci.* 140, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2013.12.031>
- Vis, M., Klijn, F., De Bruijn, K.M., Van Buuren, M., 2003. Resilience strategies for flood risk management in the Netherlands. *Int. J. River Basin Manag.* 1, 33–40. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15715124.2003.9635190>
- Vörösmarty, C.J., Rodríguez Osuna, V., Cak, A.D., Bhaduri, A., Bunn, S.E., Corsi, F., Gastelumendi, J., Green, P., Harrison, I., Lawford, R., Marcotullio, P.J., McClain, M., McDonald, R., McIntyre, P., Palmer, M., Robarts, R.D., Szöllösi-Nagy, A., Tessler, Z., Uhlenbrook, S., 2018. Ecosystem-based water security and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). *Ecohydrol. Hydrobiol.* 18, 317–333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecohyd.2018.07.004>
- Wharton, G., Gilvear, D.J., 2007. River restoration in the UK: Meeting the dual needs of the European Union water framework directive and flood defence? *Int. J. River Basin Manag.* 5, 143–154. doi:10.1080/15715124.2007.9635314
- Wondolleck, J., Yafee, S.L., 2000. Making collaboration work: Lessons from innovation in natural resource management. Island Press, Washington D.C.
- Wasserman, S., Faust, K., 1995. Social network analysis, methods and applications. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Wedel, M., Kamakura, W., 2000. Market segmentation: Conceptual and methodological foundations. Kluwer, Dordrecht, The Netherlands.